

Pragmatic Functions of Inquiry Speech Acts in Balinese Youtube Content

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Abstract

This study aims to discover the pragmatic functions of inquiry speech act that are used in Balinese YouTube Content. The data source of this study is a video which is taken from one of the famous Balinese YouTube accounts namely "Taksu North Bali" entitled "Bungut sing Mepajak". The data were analyzed descriptively and qualitatively and supported with observation methods and note-taking techniques. All of the data were analyzed by using the theory from Searle (1969) and Halliday and Hasan (1989) to find out the pragmatic function of the utterance. The findings showed that pragmatic functions in this video can be combined into 5, namely 1) inquiry to take directive action, 2) inquiry to convey representative action, 3) inquiry to take commissive action, 4) inquiry to submit expressive action and 5) inquiry to take declarative action. From the data, it was also found that the pragmatic function of inquiry sentences in Balinese when the participant has a close kinship relationship is to state a situation, ask someone else to do something, criticize a situation, express willingness to do something in the future, and judge others.

1. Introduction

A language is a tool that can be used to communicate in society (Ndiaye & Camaco, 2021). Communication can be done orally and using written language. Verbal communication usually occurs in the form of conversation by direct interaction between two or more participants to achieve a goal (Rahmayani et al., 2022). In understanding the contents of a conversation, it is necessary to pay attention to the context of the conversation. However, sometimes the participants involved do not pay attention to the context so the pragmatic function of speech cannot be understood properly.

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In communicating, several forms of language can be used, one of which is the form of questions. In using this form of language, it is hoped that there will be an active response that arises from the speaker after hearing the questions posed by the speaker (Djahimo, 2020; Hombing, H. B., & Sipahutar, 2022). The form of the question used besides having a function according to the form can also be studied from a pragmatic perspective. The pragmatic side that is intended relates to the external side of language which carries out a certain function such as a message function (asking for information, suggestions, confirmation, etc.), carrying out relationships, interactions, and the context of language use (Searle, 1969:14).

According to Yule (1996), pragmatics is a study of the relations among linguistic structures and their users. Pragmatics is concerned with the study of interpretation as it is delivered by the speaker or writer and understood by the hearer or reader (Yule, 1996:3). When the context is known, the meaning of the language can be comprehended. The assumed meaning may vary based on how, when, and where the speech is made (Kusumarini et al., 2021). In other words, context influences meaning, such as how statements are perceived in different contexts.

The interesting thing in the study of pragmatics is that every form of language can have a pragmatic function that may be different from the function of the sentence. As in the form of language, the question does not only function to ask questions but can also function pragmatically in terms of context. The purpose of this study is to analyze the pragmatic function of the use of illocutionary speech acts of questions that appear in Balinese content on YouTube. The account selected in the data source is the local YouTube account "Taksu North Bali" which is famous for its short comedy videos and the performers use the Balinese dialect of Buleleng.

The use of videos in this YouTube account certainly has a reason (Maulana et al., 2020). Besides this account being famous for its comedy videos, this account has a large number of subscribers, and the videos it produces are full of moral messages whose stories revolve around everyday life in society. The use of simple language uses various forms of language and has a pragmatic function. Therefore, the researcher made one of the short videos on "Taksu North Bali's" YouTube account as a research object with a research focus on analyzing pragmatic functions in question speech acts.

2. Material and Method

Illocutionary Act

The illocutionary act occurs through the communicative force of an utterance. Illocutionary acts are statements made with a specific purpose in mind. Someone could say something, offer something, explain, or any other type of communication (Yule, 1996:48; Putra et al., 2022; Sumarta et al., 2022). Searle (1969) divided illocutionary speech acts into 5 categories, they are:

1) Representative

A representative is a speech act that binds the speaker to the truth of something he said. Included in this act, are examples of stating, telling, complaining, expressing opinions, and reporting;

2) Directive

This illocution aims to produce an effect in the form of an action carried out by the speaker, for example, ordering, ordering, begging, demanding, and giving advice;

3) Commissive

In this illocutionary, the speaker is bound to act in the future, for example, promising, offering, and vowing;

4) Expressive

This illocutionary function expresses the speaker's psychological attitude towards conditions implied in the illocutionary, for example expressing thanks, congratulating, apologizing, criticizing, praising, pleasantries, and condolences;

5) Declarative

The successful implementation of this illocutionary effect results in correspondence between the contents of the proposition and reality. For example, resigning baptizing, dismissing, naming, sentencing, and appointing employees.

This study utilized the theory of Halliday and Hasan (1989) also to find out the pragmatic function of each utterance. They discuss three aspects of the context of a situation in their book *"Language, Context, and Text: Aspects of Language in a Social-Semiotic Perspective,"* which are field, tenor, and mode. The specifics of the aspects are as follows;

1) Field

The term "field" describes what is happening, the type of social action that is occurring, what the individuals are doing, and how some crucial element of language is involved (Halliday and Hasan, 1989:10). In short, the field refers to a part of the situation's context that addresses the topic or subject matter of the conversation, such as where, what is happening, why, and what the participants are doing.

2) Tenor

The term "tenor" refers to who is involved, what they are participating in, how they are participating, and what their status and roles are. It also refers to the different roles that each person is connected to through both temporary and permanent ties, both in the speech role they have in a conversation and in all of the interpersonal interactions that are socially significant to them (Halliday and Hasan, 1989:10).

3) Mode

The term "mode" describes the role that language is serving and the participants' expectations of what the language will do for them in that circumstance. It also refers to the text's status, its function, and its symbolic organization within the context, as well as the channel (whether it is written, spoken, or a combination), and the rhetorical mode, or what the text is trying to accomplish in terms of being expository, didactic, persuasive, and the like (Halliday and Hasan, 1989:10)

Methods

Qualitative descriptive research is included in this study. The data for this study is a Balinese parody video titled "Bungut sing Mepajak" from Taksu North Bali's YouTube account. This comedy video features Balinese illocutionary speaking performances delivered spontaneously in the Buleleng dialect of Bali. This video is full of moral lessons that individuals see daily. This study's data collection methods and techniques included the uninvolved conversation observation approach and note-taking approach. The data was then qualitatively evaluated using Searle's (1969) theory of speech acts and theory from Halliday and Hasan (1989) about context of situation. The examined data and the conclusions are presented in a thorough descriptive explanation using informal approaches connected to the pragmatic function of inquiry speech acts.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the results of the study, it was found that pragmatic functions can be combined into 5, namely 1) inquiry to take directive action, 2) inquiry to convey representative acts, 3) inquiry to take commissive act, 4) inquiry to submit expressive act and 5) inquiry to take declarative act. Below will be discussed the results of research that has been conducted as a form of analysis of the pragmatic function of inquiry Balinese speech acts.

Inquiry to Convey Directive Actions

Searle (1969) explains directives are an illocutionary act that attempts by the speaker to get the hearer to do something. They express what they want directly to the hearer. It commonly appears with some performative verbs such as: requesting, demanding, questioning, asking, proposing, advising, suggesting, interrogating, urging, encouraging, inviting, begging, ordering, etc. In data 1 below can be seen the use of directive action.

Data 1

- Wife : **'*kayang bungut jani mepajak bli, eh aje bli, tanggal kude jani?*'**
'Sampai mulut sekarang berpajak pak, oh iya, sekarang tanggal berapa?'
'Until the mouth is now taxed sir, oh yes, what date is today?'
- Husband : *'yéé...cai care pegawai negeri, ngitungan tanggal dén.'*
'Yee.... kamu seperti pegawai negeri, ngurusin tanggal terus.'
'Yee...you are like a civil servant, keep on taking care of the date.'

The conversation above happens when a husband and wife are talking about the problems of life they are experiencing. The problem is related to neighbors who often gossip about them. The husband is motivating his wife by saying that nowadays everyone is free to say anything because lips don't pay taxes. The wife then responds to her husband's motivational sentence with an interrogative sentence **'*kayang bungut jani mepajak bli, eh aje bli, tanggal kude jani?*'** The bold utterance in data 1 above was conveyed by using the interrogative sentence. The utterance above contains questions. In the utterance, the speaker asks the interlocutor to inform what date it is. Judging from the context, the question in the utterance does not only aim to ask something but also conveys directive actions. The function is to ask other people to take an action. The speaker wants to remind the hearer to immediately pay the Land and Building Tax that is due. Directive actions with indirect form are used by the speaker to the hearer who has a close kinship relationship, namely the relationship between husband and wife who are no longer separated and know the character of each partner.

Inquiry to Deliver Representative Actions

Searle (1969) states representatives are types of illocutionary acts that commit the speaker to believe something the truth or not. In performing this type of illocutionary act, it can be noted by some performative verbs, such as state, tell, assert, correct, predict, report, remind, described, inform, assure, agree, guess, claim, believe, conclude, etc. The use of representative action in this video can be seen in data 2 below.

Data 2

- Husband : **'*adi bengong nyai luh?*'**
'Kamu kok bengong?'

'Why are you staring?'

- Wife : *'to pisagané, adi ade jeleme kené-kené, mare waké ngidang abedik, ube omongané.'*
'Itu tetangga kita, kok ada orang kayak gitu, baru saya agak mapan sedikit, langsung di omongin.'
 'That's our neighbor, how come there are people like that, I'm just a little more settled, and they talk about it right away.'

The utterance is delivered at the beginning of the comedy. This conversation happens between husband and wife in their livestock pen. The husband is hoeing, while the wife just sits silently with a somber face. Seeing this strange habit the husband approached and asked his wife '**adi bengong nyai luh?**' or in English it translate 'Why are you staring?' This inquiry sentence contains representative actions. The sentence conveyed in the form of a question, literally functions to ask for some information regarding the condition of the wife. Based on the context, the speaker states a statement of truth about something he believes. The speaker conveys in his speech '*adi bengong nyai luh*'. In this speech, the speaker states the condition of his wife, who was sitting alone, silent with a blank stare. His wife's behavior seemed worrying for her husband because it was different from the habits of his wife who was always talkative.

Inquiry to Deliver Expressive Actions

According to Searle (1969) expressive is a kind of illocutionary act that states what the speaker feels. They express psychological states and can be statements of pleasure, pain, likes, dislikes, joy or sorrow, surprise, apology, and thank. In using expressive, the speaker makes words fit the world (of feeling). In performing an expressive, it can be noted with some performative verbs: greet, surprise, like, fear, apology, thank, regret, and praise. The use of expressive action in this video can be seen in data 3 below.

Data 3

- Huband : *'Luh, to sube keregegin nyai, sing med-med nguél nyai uli semengan. Luh, begini dah kamu, ga bosan-bosan ngoceh dari pagi.'*
 'Luh, this is how you are, don't get tired of talking from the morning.'
- Wife : ***'bli, né nak curhatan hidup adané, cuma ingin mengeluarkan isi hati, cuma heran bli, sing medmed waké omonginé, mare awaké metutup, orahané awake males, lengit, nyanan mare awaké mebukak, ramé nak meblanje, orahane awaké ngubuh babi ngepet, indik jeleme ento?'***

'Pak, ini namanya curhatan hidup, cuma ingin mengeluarkan isi hati, cuma heran Pak, ga bosan-bosan ngomongin kita, baru warung ditutup, dibilang males, entar sudah dibuka, banyak yang beli dibilang melihara babi ngepet, manusia itu?'

'Dad, this is called a life story, I just want to express my feelings, I'm just surprised, they don't get tired of talking about us when the stall was closed, and they said I was lazy when it was opened, many people bought and they said I raised witch pigs, is that human?'

The bold sentence is uttered by the wife to her husband. Here she wants to explain the feeling that she felt at that time about their neighbor. She is pouring out her heart to her husband about social phenomena that exist in society and are befalling her. She told of her turmoil about the behavior of her neighbors who always talked about her life. Questions are submitted in the form of a question tag with the Balinese marker **"jeleme ento"** or *is that human?* In the utterances of the questions submitted, they contain expressive action which serves to criticize the behavior of their neighbors. Speech acts that function to criticize are conveyed by the speaker so that the hearer can feel the turmoil felt by the speaker.

Inquiry to Deliver Commissive Actions

Searle (1969) argues commissives are a kind of illocutionary act that commits the speaker to some future course of action. In performing this type of illocutionary act, commonly using performative verbs such as: ask, order, command, request, beg, plead, pray, entreat, invite, permit, advise, dare, defy, and challenge. Below can be seen the use of commissive action in this video.

Data 4

- Husband : *'adah maksud awaké, kita adalah orang yang mampu menghadapi cobaan dan godaan, kecuali...'*
'Adah maksudku, kita adalah orang yang mampu menghadapi cobaan dan godaan, kecuali...'
 'Aaah... I mean, we are people who can face trials and temptations, except...'
- Wife : **'kecuali ape biin?'**
'Kecuali apa lagi?'
 'Except what else?'
- Husband : *'godaan setan yang ada dihadapanku.'*
 'Satan's temptations are in front of me.'

In this part, this couple is still talking about their lives which are always used as material for other people's conversations. Here, the bold sentence is used by the wife to his husband. She said **"kecuali apa biin...?"** this interrogative sentence is a kind of commissive action because in this sentence the speaker carries out what is stated in the speech which functions to express ability. Here this wife is not only asking for information from his husband, but she needs clarification about his husband's future actions related to his statement and of course, his ability when he said *"'adah maksud awaké, kita adalah orang yang mampu menghadapi cobaan dan godaan, kecuali...'*. His husband's statement is not complete, so then she needs to follow up on the sentence. Based on this continuation sentence, makes his wife feel blush.

Inquiry to Deliver Declarative Actions

Searle (1969) defines declarative as are kind of illocutionary act that changes the world via their utterances. As the example below, the speaker has to have a special institutional role, in a specific context such as to pronounce, declare, baptize, and sentence. The words that can be indicated in this type are the curse, announce, declare, define, appoint, call, bless, nominate, and authorized. In data 5 below, can be seen the use of a declarative function.

Data 5

- Huband : **'badah... telat nyai? Alih-alihan kenyat, biin nyai telat.'**
 'Ya ampun...telat kamu...? Pemasukan susah, terus kamu telat'

Wife	'Are you late...? Income is difficult, then you are determined' : 'bli naké ngingetan, amen sube mease do oyongange, enggalin.' 'Kamu rasa-rasain dong, kalo udah berasa jangan didiemin, cepetin' 'You can taste it, if you feel it, don't let it go, hurry up'
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This conversation is found at the end of the video. This husband asks his wife by uttering this sentence '*badah... telat nyai?*' This sentence is usually used to ask about a condition, but based on the context the husband here is not asking a question but he judges his wife. It can be seen from the next sentence that following this inquiry sentence delivered from the husband '*Alih-alihan kenyat, biin nyai telat.*' This sentence emphasizes the accusations made by the husband against his wife. He thinks his wife was pregnant even though it was late what his wife meant was not late for her period but late paying taxes.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis, speech act in the form of Balinese inquiry has a pragmatic function that can be reduced to five namely 1) inquiry to take directive action, 2) inquiry to convey representative acts, 3) inquiry to take commissive act, 4) inquiry to submit expressive act and 5) inquiry to take declarative act. These five pragmatic functions are obtained from the speech act of inquiry uttered by the participant in this video. Thus, an interrogative sentence does not only function to ask questions about certain information, but the function may vary depending on the context. In this case, the illocutionary speech act used by the husband has representative and declarative pragmatic functions, while the wife's questions have directive, expressive, and commissive pragmatic functions. The function of inquiry sentences in Balinese, when the participant has a close kinship relationship, is to state a situation, ask someone else to do something, criticize a situation, express willingness to do something in the future, and judge others.

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References

- Djahimo, S. E. (2020). The Influence of Specific Usage of Address Terms in Kupang Malay Language on Changing Attitudes and Shifting Perceptions. *The International Journal of Language and Cultural (TIJOLAC)*, 2(02), 39-51.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Hasan, R. (1989). *Language, context, and text: Aspects of language in a social-semiotic perspective (2nd ed.)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hombing, H. B., & Sipahutar, C. A. (2022). Implementation of 'ruth and naomi' interpersonal communication as a model in avoiding toxic relationship. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 4(1), 424-431.
- Kusumarini, I., Simpen, I. W., Budiarsa, M., & Laksana, I. K. D. (2021). Politeness Strategy of Japanese Hotel Staff in Bali. *The International Journal of Language and Cultural (TIJOLAC)*, 3(01), 9-28.
- Maulana, E., Suhud, U., Susono, J., Buchdadi, A. D., & Amiruddin, K. (2020). Measuring YouTube Channel Subscriber Loyalty: The Role of Quality, Corporate Image and Viewer Satisfaction. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 2(2), 32-39.
- Ndiaye, M., & Camaco, G. (2021). Children with Developmental Language Disorder: A Proposal for the Future Project. *The International Journal of Language and Cultural (TIJOLAC)*, 3(01), 1-8.
- Putra, E. D., Simpen, I. W., Sudipa, I. N., & Sedeng, I. N. (2022). Speech act in the learning process of a bilingual school. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 4(2), 232-240.
- Rahmayani, A., Nurhaeni, I. D. A., & Satyawan, I. A. (2022). Family communication of health workers during the covid-19 pandemic: A review of interaction adaptation. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 4(2), 45-53.
- Searle, John. R. (1969). *Speech Act: An Essay on the Philosophy of Language*. New York. Cambridge University Press.
- Sumarta, I. W. A., Simpen, I. W., Laksana, I. K. D., & Artawa, K. (2022). Turn-taking and cooperation principles on "Catatan Demokrasi Kita" and its implications in Indonesian language learning. *The International Journal of Language and Cultural (TIJOLAC)*, 4(1), 77-85.
- Yule, G. (1996). *Pragmatics*. New York, Oxford University Express.